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<https://doi.org/10.61796/ejheaa.v1i7.753>**LEADERSHIP IN ISLAMIC EDUCATION****Rizky Hanivan¹, Ahmad Balya Adiba²**^{1,2}Islamic Education Management Department

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Abstract: This paper is a brief discussion of leadership in Islamic education management. Leadership is an activity in guiding a group so that the goals of the group are achieved, namely common goals. Leadership is an obligation if an organization wants to run effectively. Effective leadership indicates leadership delivered by a leader who is authoritative and wise in implementing his leadership strategy in order to realize the vision and mission that is held firmly by himself and his team and lead many people in a better direction. Because, leaders in organizations are managers who carry out management functions. A leader can carry out his role by providing assistance, namely by creating a good climate, the leader can also help the group in establishing work procedures. So this article aims to provide an overview of the role of leadership in improving the performance of educational institutions. Therefore, it is necessary to implement leadership functions in order to progress an organization. This paper was selected using the library research method by collecting various written sources to obtain conclusions from this research.

Keywords: Leadership, Management, Islamic Education.

This is an open-access article under the [CC-BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) licenses**Introduction**

Leadership is a process of influencing subordinates regarding activities that have been determined, planned and organized to achieve specified goals. Leadership is also a very important factor in an organization. Very often, the good or bad of an organization is largely influenced by leadership factors. Therefore, all organizations definitely need a leader to lead the organization so that the planned goals are achieved. Included in this is the organization of educational institutions, whose leaders are usually called school principals.

In general, leadership can be understood as a leader who is able to direct, develop or organize, guide and also show or influence. And educational institutions are a useful forum for developing people, leading them towards a better future. Leadership in educational institutions can be referred to as someone who holds the authority to determine the development of educational institutions (Syarifuddin, 2021). According to Ginanjar (2006), thousands of people hope to become leaders. They often don't realize that they are their own leaders. When a child is class president then he is a leader. The RT head is also a leader, a teacher is a leader for his students, even a mother is a leader for her children. Almost everyone becomes a leader in their respective environment regardless of the size of the number of people in the group. Even though there is only one follower, he is still said to be a leader. Even humans alone must be able to lead themselves.

In its implementation, the leader has the power to mobilize and influence his subordinates regarding the tasks that must be carried out. At the task assignment stage, the leader must provide clear direction and guidance, so that subordinates can carry out their duties easily and the results achieved are in accordance with the goals that have been set. Thus, leadership includes an unequal distribution of power between the leader and his members. Leaders have the authority to direct members and can also exert influence, in other words leaders can not only order subordinates what to do, but can also influence how subordinates carry out their orders. So that a social relationship that interacts with each other between leaders and subordinates is established, which Finally, a reciprocal relationship occurs. Therefore, leaders are expected to have the ability to carry out their leadership, because if they do not have the ability to lead, then the goals they want to achieve will not be achieved optimally.

Leadership is also a combination of three main components, namely the basic situation and conditions or environment, faced by the leader, supported by followers and filled with communication. These three components provide a balanced contribution to considering the leadership model. It can also be stated that the situations and conditions that occur become favorable conditions in the hands of leaders who involve and empower followers. Understanding that leadership involves interactions between the leader, followers, and the situation. Leadership involves dynamic interactions between leaders and followers in specific situations. Leadership studies must include followers and their situations. The interactive nature of leader-follower situations is the changing nature of leader-follower relationships and the increasing complexity of situations faced by leaders and followers. Good leadership can be enhanced by greater awareness of the factors that influence the leadership process. Overall, the factors that influence leadership are described as the existence of leaders, followers and goals as potential components which are supported by the achievement component, namely commitment and the process of influencing to achieve goals (commitment, influence, achieve).

Methods

When writing this paper, you must definitely have a method for writing it, namely related to how the data obtained in this paper is treated, such as related to data sources, data collection techniques, and so on as support in the formation of this paper.

One of the important things in writing this paper is related to data collection, because according to Sugiyono, data collection techniques are very important to carry out as a strategic effort to obtain data in research.

In writing this paper, it was written using the literature study method or often referred to as (library research). This is a series of activities related to library data collection methods by reading, taking notes and processing research materials originating from library data such as reference books or journals so that they are not bound by field data.

As also said, according to Sugiyono, library research can be carried out by obtaining secondary research data and conducting studies on these theories based on library research such as books, journals, magazines, or other results. previous research that has been published, or sources that are appropriate to the topic and are still related to the literature.

Results and Discussion

3.1 Definition of Leadership

Etymologically, leadership in English, namely leadership, contains three words that have meaning, namely lead (leading), leader, and leadership. Lead is leading, guiding, leading and directing. Lead is an activity carried out (leading). This is the word doing, it is all about the interpersonal manifestation of leading, guiding, leading and directing. These are all the main jobs that leaders do. A leader is a person who leads, guides, directs and directs. Leadership is the process of leading, guiding, guiding and directing, namely a reciprocal process between the leader and those being led, and the situation or conditions faced. In other words, leadership is a guiding process carried out by leaders towards those they lead with empathetic communication to solve problems faced in a particular situation or condition.

In general, it can also be interpreted that leadership is the ability to influence and motivate a group or people towards achieving a goal. A manager who does not have a leadership spirit tends to be impersonal and passive towards goals, while a person who has a leadership spirit tends to take a personal and active attitude towards goals. Leadership is more about things that are done to overcome change by setting direction through developing a vision of the future and allying with other people through communication and inspiring existing communication to find solutions to overcome existing problems.

The word diction used by the Apostle when generalizing the functions and responsibilities of each individual as a leader at all strata is *ra'i*. This word can be referred to in a fragment of the Prophet's hadith which reads..." *Kullukum ra'in, wakullukum mas'ulun 'an raiyaitihi...*". Literally this word means "shepherd". The use of this word in referring to the leader of each individual of his people is very strong, due to the Apostle's background as a shepherd. If we look closely, the profession as a shepherd turns out to provide many lessons for the Apostle in building the foundation for his leadership in the future. This job, according to Harahap, teaches him to be responsible for the sheep he shepherds so that they are orderly in the flock. This work also requires love, such as looking for sheep that are separated from the herd or caring for sick sheep. With responsibility and a feeling of love, the shepherd leads the animals being grazed to the destination point, including leading them when they return home from the pen.

In Islam, leadership is so important that it receives great attention. Leadership is so important, it requires every association to have a leader, even small groups. The Prophet Muhammad said, which means: "From Abu Sa'id from Abu Hurairah, both of them said, Rasulullah SAW said: When three people go out traveling, let one of them be the leader." (HR. Abu Daud). Based on this hadith, the right to elect a leader is in the hands of the community (congregation). It is not permissible for someone to claim and elevate himself to be a leader, and force the community to obey his leadership. A true leader is a person who is chosen by society, because he has certain characteristics that are different from others, and he gets the approval of the majority of society, even though not completely. Leadership emerged with human civilization, namely since the time of the prophets and human ancestors. Since then there has been cooperation between people, and there is an element of leadership. Leadership is a matter of the relationship between the leader and those led. Leadership emerges and develops as a result of automatic interactions between the leader and the individuals being led.

3.2. Leadership Model

There are 3 leadership models in management science, including:

- a) Charismatic leadership
This leadership comes from God's gift or talent where the person can lead and has extraordinary abilities. This ability is like a strong magnet with a strong emotional attraction from a leader to the people he leads. Examples include Bung Karno, Mahatma Gandhi, and Anwar Sadat .
- b) Transactional leadership
This leadership is used to implement mutually beneficial transactions with subordinates, manage subordinates by giving rewards and also consumers. Transactional leadership is usually to control subordinates by using power to achieve results.
- c) Transformational leadership
This leadership model is quite effective and is widely applied in various national and international organizations.

3.3. Islamic Leadership Work Ethic

The Duties of Leadership Islam views that every human being sent down on earth is a leader. Humans as khalifatullah are given the responsibility to submit and obey the commands of Allah SWT. This is a function and role inherent in humans. There are several important tasks in leadership, namely:

1. As Counselor.
This is part of the duties of a leader in a work unit, to be a helper and assist human resources in a work unit in resolving work problems which are the responsibility of the work of every human resource in an organization. In dealing with problems, leaders are expected to be able to provide counseling so that they can answer the problems they face.
2. As an Instructor
Whatever rank a leader is at, he or she has the responsibility of being an instructor in the task at hand, being a director of the human resources that make up the work tool. The task as an instructor is to be a wise teacher, which will produce human resources who work professionally in completing tasks.
3. Able to Lead Meetings.
At any level, a leader can allocate time to sit together with his work equipment. To achieve the expected goals, a plan is needed to be able to realize shared hopes. In planning goals, the leader must sit down with the work apparatus to formulate a method that is mutually agreed upon and carried out according to the plan formed. The leader must be able to move all the work tools according to their abilities so that they can run smoothly. appropriate.
4. Decision-making.
The difference between a leader is in decision making, making the right decision in a critical situation requires fast thinking skills from every leader, from all the tasks that are the fundamental requirements of a dreamer, this is quite a tough task in the decision making process. (Edy Sutrisno, 2009: 233)
5. Testing Feasibility.
Leaders must test whether work programs in an organization are feasible or not. Every organization must have a program to achieve the common goals of an organization

6. Evaluate.

A leader must be able to observe well in each activity to evaluate the shortcomings of each activity carried out in order to be able to do better in carrying out the next activity. Evaluation is an important process to correct the work that has been done. (Priansa, 2016: 149)

When working, a Muslim must have an Islamic work ethic, which includes:

1. Professional. In carrying out work, every Muslim is required to be serious in order to obtain the best results. Of course, to achieve professionalism it must be supported by scientific, modern and sophisticated facilities.
2. Persistent. Work is not just a requirement that must be completed, but work for Muslims emphasizes working diligently and well, namely by completing it perfectly because that is the obligation of every Muslim.
3. Honest. In the view of Muslims, work is seen as worship, not just fulfilling human needs in the world. By drawing closer to Allah SWT, every Muslim will work well solely to meet the needs of this world and the hereafter.
4. Creative. If today is the same as yesterday then a person like this is at a loss, because he is left behind and there is no progress in a person like this who is worse and worse off is the person whose today is worse than yesterday so he is left behind and will find it difficult to catch up. Luckily for everyone who is better today than yesterday, then there is progress within the p-ISSN 2654-3923 e-ISSN 2621-6051 SYARIKAT: Journal of Sharia Economic Group Volume 3, Number 1, June 2020 16 people, this is Changes and attitudes are expected to always occur in a Muslim, so that he will not be left behind in terms of work, always accept change and be ready to respond to change in any case. (Malacca, 2013: 61)
5. Discipline. A person who has a good level of discipline will be careful in completing his work with full responsibility. His heart and profession are aligned and focused on the results that are his goals so that he is able to adapt to the toughest situations. Disciplined individuals have adaptability and flexibility to adapt to innovation and new ideas.

Responsible. It can be interpreted as trust which is faith which is taken from the origin of the word amnun which means security or peace, which is the opposite of the words "worry, worry or fear", something which belongs to someone else and is in your hands is called trust because it is in your hands. You don't worry, worry or fear the owner of the item because you will feel reassured that you will look after it and if asked, you will hand it over.

Conclusion

Leadership in education is the ability to influence the implementation of educational goals effectively and efficiently. In the context of Islamic education, it involves guiding spiritual and physical growth according to Islamic teachings through wisdom, direction, teaching, training, nurturing, and supervision. Thus, Islamic leadership is the ability to direct the implementation of all Islamic teachings. In Islamic educational institutions, this leadership is embodied by the school principal, who plays a crucial role in determining the institution's success. Basic Islamic educational leadership emphasizes educating and guiding, with a focus on increasing knowledge. A leader in this context should possess seven prophetic characteristics: shidiq (honesty), trustworthy (trustworthiness), tabligh (ability to convey), fathanah (intelligence), istiqamah (consistency), mahabbah (love and compassion), and pious/ma'ruf (goodness and wisdom).

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